

Effective Teams for the Corporate World

Sara Safa Neama

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Abstract: Teamwork would be needed to succeed competitively in the global open economy. For the corporate world, the use of a team-based system is no longer simply a waste resource for increasing the business quality of service. The use of successful teams has proven critical in today's developing economies to sustain businesses' long-term stability and growth. Centred on the duplication of human resources, it has been not easy for corporate to distinguish themselves from the competition. And businesses must have perseverance and resilience in a world of continuous transition, to keep up with team growth. It isn't so hard to run a team, but it is a struggle to make a team successful. If teams do not gain efficiency, it can be time-consuming, but teams may yield previously elusive outcomes if they become efficient. The research involves a review of applicable literature. This research involves interviews with corporate in Erbil, Kurdistan, on which factors successful teams produce. The findings derived from these interviews were transcribed and analysed against the key research and the variations between them.

Keywords: Team Roles, Team Work, Virtual Teams, Team Building, Communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's global economy is too diverse and changes too fast to maintain a hierarchical system for business corporate. Future corporate are exploring novel ways to encourage reactivity, performance, growth and learning. Cross-functional teams will boost flexibility and productivity for market enterprises given the complexities of execution (Cross, 1997).

The real movement of the corporate to pursue improved productivity, fewer capital, cutbacks and cut expenditures often demanded the cooperation and efficiency of the workforce. In virtually every corporate, collaboration has invaded every nook and cranny. The truth is, though, that the vast majority of the teams are not able to accomplish the synergies. A collaboration between people and challenges is the foundation for the team to work together to generate solutions and solve problems. Teams can surpass what a person can achieve on their own. Teams should draw on synergies. Each ingredient can be wonderful and fresh separately, but not to a gourmet level. Teamwork is like a salad. To obtain a surprising outcome, combinations of ingredients strengthen one another (Menzela, 1997).

In addition to improving team performance and promoting team development, people working as a team can also lead to complementary management competences. Yet only team leaders agree with each other can this method reach a high success rate. This unity is related to the alignment of the team members, which may represent their desires, ideals and beliefs. Team building is a mechanism in which managers, team members strive to work more successfully together with the individual emotions, behaviours, actions and collective engagement (Dyer, 1995).

However, promoting project innovations is not a straightforward feat for a typically hierarchical enterprise. A deliberate strategy from the outset to produce continuing successful outcomes is important to move forward in a team-based structure. Whenever a corporate is ready for the transition to a team-based system, it should have a good understanding of why it initiates teams, what adjustments in the organizational hierarchy can be made, and what the possible benefits and disadvantages might entail. When the corporate draw a successful verdict on these topics, it will initiate a team bonding program.

Background

Work teams appear to be a smart concept intuitively and are certainly a rising phenomenon. Research at the Work Teams Study Center reveals with Joinson (1999) that 80 per cent of Fortune 500 corporate would recruit half of their employees

into teams by 2000. Consultants' preliminary surveys and data show a failure rate of at least 50 per cent — but effective teams can produce good outcomes, which more than outweigh failures (Joinson, 1999).

The behaviours of teams, on the other hand, showed some disappointing effects. Some of Catalyst Consulting Group's most unexpected findings in a study of teams also had shown that more than 70 per cent of them have struggled. Ronald Recardo (1999) suggests that the lack of a systematic assessment to include longitudinal statistics on the corporate, which may act as a helpful guide to the turnaround process, is one explanation for this poor success rate.

The corporate is searching for individuals who can work and learn efficiently in teams to be creative and competitive. Corporate use teams more and more to boost efficiency, speed, creativity or loyalty with their consumers. In a high-tech environment, engagement is the rule in the workplace, according to Katzenbach and Smith (1994). The workforce is increasingly comprised of interdependent teams that collaborate on complicated problems that cannot be addressed by individuals alone (Gardner, 1998).

The Problem Statement

Creating teams with corporate jargon isn't a new term. In England since 1750, manufacturers had already developed a method of employing "teams" to improve productivity for large-scale manufacturing during the era of the industrial revolution. Today, there are several corporates in their business operation that have already established teams and who have produced good results. Many of these corporations have in practice an outdated perception of teams as working units focused on individual performance outcomes. Their lack of inspired teams has not contributed to their potential for empowering the workforce to increase the overall success of the corporate to provide more innovative approaches for improved customer satisfaction and development.

It is not an easy feat to accomplish this modern concept by using teams. It would be straightforward to suggest that a high-performance team for the corporate, but the conclusions achieved might be very different if the definition were applied. On a scientific standpoint, only a rational input method can be applied and the results have to be followed up. The findings obtained can vary significantly from what was anticipated. In certain cases, corporate don't give the teams the right weight and energy to conquer development phases. Many teams will also only produce high returns and they must be retained in corporate if they are not replaced and continue delivering existing outputs from their production lines.

The Purpose

This research is meant to recognize variables that may contribute to high-produce teams. The research will help corporate, given the obstacles, assess team building principles through careful evaluation of their application and thereby guide the enterprise as a whole to greater success. This research will introduce innovative ideas to corporate members to construct a culturally dynamic atmosphere and can promote team building continuously. The factor that indicates reasons for team building success or loss will also be exposed.

The research does not assess the effectiveness of a single team but only seeks to evaluate the characteristics of effective teams.

The purpose of this research is, therefore:

1. Identifying and evaluating successful teams' strengths.
2. Provide innovative ideas that help to create teams continuously.
3. Describe teams' perceived advantages and risks.
4. Factors showing reasons for team bonding success or failure.
5. Describe the unsuccessful squad characteristics.
6. Provide useful advice for corporate leaders to introduce or inspire teams.

Major Questions

This research could help unveil barriers to team empowerment:

1. How does a certain team not function as a whole?
2. Why is any team most of the time in conflict?

3. Why should corporate be thinking with morals and self-esteem?
4. What corporate steps to assess the success of a team will be carried out.
5. What are the potential hazards for funding teams?
6. How would be done to inspire team leaders to produce better results?

Significance

The strength of teams is extremely influential in a corporate, guiding the business to greater results or deeper failure. This is also of very considerable significance that teams are correctly measured and regarded. When a corporate mistake to incorporate teams within its sector, profitability may be impaired. The use of effective teams within an enterprise, on the other hand, may not have contributed to success beforehand.

Hypothesis

Factors producing high-performance teams are predicted from this research. Whether the analysis reflects the predicted effects of this research and demonstrates that leaders will help the corporate excel in teams. Nonetheless, more research will be needed if the findings of this research do not show any association with predicted outcomes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The present research demonstrates the processes of the design, creation and management of teams from a theoretical point of view. In turn, teams must evaluate the advantages and risks and explain the causes of the missed opportunity. Eventually, this research would offer information into future improvements to enhance cognitive ability.

Building Teams

The right team form represents the best service for the boss, the coworkers and the whole corporate. The corporate environment, cultural issues and the willingness of participants are essential to ensure a successful match in with the research to be done (Menzela, 1997).

One of the first steps for a corporate protocol is to develop a strategy by incorporating a team bonding principle. The strategy would explain how corporate is expected to accomplish and calculate its planned goals. The corporate will first persuade the members of the team to establish a mission plan expressing corporate beliefs. The declaration will represent the corporate understanding of consumer demands and approaches that can satisfy these requirements. The team formed to deal with these decisions that take a broader view of the corporate and its market place than one person may have done on his own.

Additionally, a mission statement will be established by the leadership that explains the corporate goals, the products and services it provides, the industry it represents, how the workforce will be handled and the values and philosophy of the corporate. Such contours are structured to educate clients and to direct the work of employees within the corporate. The statement of the mission should be brief and concise, to reach concrete goals. For all members of the corporate, the statement must be easy and attractive, keep the objectives in mind and commit to achieving them. When anyone remembers such a sentence, it transforms into a catalyst to produce the desired results.

Third, the team should achieve corporate objectives to define standards members should achieve in areas such as profitability, customer service, and employee satisfaction. These guides can help staff improve their confidence, support them in making suggestions for problem-solving, encourage them to make the best possible use of them and provide tangible standards for a corporate to evaluate its performance.

When developing teams, certain aspects of their creation have been thoroughly discussed. This method will affect the coordination of all organizational processes of the corporate. It is not so hard to create a team, but it is a real challenge to make the team successful. If teams are not successful, they can be considered as time-consuming, but when teams are productive they can yield a lot of results that may be worth all efforts.

To set up a squad need to take a few moves, beginning with initiating the team-building exercise and finishing with squad activities. Nonetheless, making a team effective is more difficult because it involves interaction and communication between the team members, aspects that go beyond the corporate direct control and power.

The following basic steps to build teams are analyzed in this research: the selection of teams, clarity of team roles, suggested teamwork and goal setting as the commitment to teams.

Selection of Teams

Selection of team members is the first step in building a squad. The collection will consist of a staff of the corporate that may assist in the issue or the future reform directly. The selected individuals should have high interpersonal analytical and technical qualifications that must be evaluated according to the composition of the team. The team members will aim to obtain the widest diversity of viewpoints from a range of individuals with various individualities, abilities and experiences. The effective team must include leaders who are empowered and prepared to adapt, cultivate trust and faith, communicate openly, listen carefully, value diversity, encourage fair engagement and participate in ongoing learning, and increase the cohesion of the team (Scholtes, Joiner & Streibel, 1996).

Senior management teams are becoming more popular in diversity – and performance promotes diversity. The higher business success is a combination of gender, racial origin and aged in senior management teams. Senior executives under the age of 40 had a larger history of performance than businesses with exclusively top management. Because the different people working together pose perceived challenges and conflicts, the starting teams can be formed. This is today's strategic benefit to bring workforce united – not just as a community of individuals but as a team committed to achieving its goal. By encouraging people to do their best and to improve their interest in the group, corporate build intelligent teams that accomplish their tasks (Farren, 1999).

A team should be fairly broad to include members who have similar competences who are limited enough to benefit from teamwork. It will be more successful if a team is responsible for a variety of activities than if separate teams are responsible for competing objectives. Celebrating diversity is the secret to stronger team ties. Taking advantage of different designs (Huszczko, 1996).

Clarity of Team Roles

As the second step of team building, team leaders will know their position in the team well. The results of team projects can differ greatly based on how much people are aware of the priorities, procedures, context and orientation of other members of the team. The personality, intellectual competences, beliefs and opinions on "how things are done" form the basis for other people's views on "how things are to be done." These conclusions are not a concern because everyone knows the same thing, but if they do not, it poses a barrier to team effectiveness. So it is important to learn how to remove the barrier to boost interactions, to produce more innovations and to build new goods and services (Haight, 1999).

This is also important for the team to decide from the very beginning on its positions. The members of the team might answer the questions: "Why am I here? And "What can I help that team?" Team members have roles and responsibilities following the corporate and the activities they will perform. There are usually three positions: sponsor, stakeholder and steering committee.

A sponsor is a person who must ensure frequent analysis of duties and obligations and obey them most importantly. The key duty of the sponsor is to work closely with both parties to ensure positive development and that every person fulfils his / her obligations and responsibilities. If not, the sponsor is accountable, the duty and responsibility to ensure that the appropriate corrective action is pursued.

The stakeholders bring value by participating in this journey; the team must also ensure that members are updated regularly as the process progresses. This regular update enhances the quality of the data used by capturing errors and reduces surveillance levels.

To review the team's course and development concerning the deliverables, values, details and scope, the steering committee will outline the activities so far periodically. Special theoretical questions will be posted by steering committee members: Are we still on the course? Will new details need to be taken into account? Will the team need some help? Does there have to be eliminated any barriers? Is there supposed to have additional resources?

Suggested Team Work

This method calls for a great deal of effort from team leaders to excel in these activities. Members must dedicate themselves entirely to contributing to team goals. They will then set off their agendas and avoid interruptions outside team concerns when "clustering," which are necessary to improve team cohesion and contribution to team activities across team-related issues. Team members also need to balance their daily work responsibilities with their team activity. A well-working team will concentrate on problem management, consensus-based decision-making, project creation and task-taking.

The question is that there are unseen problems that take team members away from their apparent duties, including events. As they reach a meeting through the entrance, team leaders become overcome by mixed emotions: apprehension and enthusiasm over team composition, commitment to their departments and branches, an anxious expectation of the progress of the mission. Unattended, these resulting changes will hinder the possibility for a group to become a successful team. Therefore, each team must take time to do tasks that are not directly linked with a mission, to facilitate awareness and cooperation within the community.

Even though teams need to be flexible in developing their activities, it is also important to determine the borderline of a team to ensure that the team does not exceed the limit and/or do something not covered by the business plans for the corporate. To facilitate this autonomy and to create team boundaries, corporate also promote the formation of sub-teams to work more narrowly on their assignments.

Goal Setting as a Commitment to Teams

Teams will have a purpose as a fixed goal on both sides: the course of the corporate and focus of the teams. This collaborative guide is an effective match for sustaining a positive atmosphere and producing incremental success at the end. It should support team responsibilities at all levels as defined goals, while at the same time, it should be committed to team members with defined goals in the corporate direction. Personal friendships may only result in an improvement in success, according to recent studies, when friends are firmly committed to the interests of the community or corporate (Ross, 1997).

To be successful, team leaders must meet with requirements such as a multiplicity of competences and a passion for success, as they dedicate themselves to a shared purpose. Besides, each team member must contribute in an innovative and original; natural and spontaneous way. Any participant has a chance to contribute their opinions to debates, they need to be obliged.

Communication

When developing partnerships, collaboration is a crucial word for progress. Misunderstandings will as far as possible be stopped. Identify potential variations in attitudes and conduct of team leaders. Identify the possible differences, identify possibilities and possible pitfalls, and outline specific scenarios. Teams cannot thrive if members are jealous of their tasks and see others' support as a setback for themselves. Rather of dismissed, seek to confront this adverse behaviour (Menzela, 1997).

The formation of positive connections between team members involves open communication. Members should be able, without fear of reproach, to express their opinions freely and feel that suggestions are taken seriously. The team will be expected to decide on whether to manage within the boundaries of their department or to interact with other workers politically related topics of conversation at meetings (Yeung, 1999).

Team members shouldn't make previous decisions about an uncertain situation so that false assumptions can be avoided. Teamwork requires working by consensus to make decisions that are of mutual interest to all members. It might not be the first choice to reach consensus, but it is a choice everyone will accept with an appreciation of why it is better (Scholtes et al., 1996). Thus, to keep going ahead and be successful, team leaders must find consensus and agreement in their decisions. Besides, although a team member feels uncomfortable in deciding the team, the team should reassess that decision and work to achieve consensus. This process helps all team members to be respected and taken into consideration.

Virtual Teams

To meet without direct contact and consequently, team members need no longer be housed in one location to work together with fewer communication resources. Virtual teams are seen as an intelligent way of organizing for flexible and cost-efficient operation with recent technological advantages. Teams may become automated for the normal intent of transversal time zones, distances and corporate boundaries through technologies.

Networks can help teams prevent fragmentation and isolation in team-based organizations. The network, not the pyramid, is a paradigm for people working together to accomplish goals. The most convenient way to switch between hierarchy and bureaucracy is to attach ties to the relation feature. Communication flows directly between the individuals and those who need information. Persons are at the heart of collaborative communities and all team members must be independent, self-sufficient but also interdependent.

Global market technology has brought millions of people new friends and new ways of operating. Throughout its scope, languages and societies, the proliferation of ties across each possible frontier is stagnating; governments and human

behaviour both play a role. Professor Robert Putman of Harvard said there are three elements needed for the creation of social capital: trust, reciprocity and large social networks. People ought to believe that giving inevitably contributes to receiving. People prefer to be safer and more socially secure in the corporate of strongly linked individuals in large social networks (Lipnack, 1999).

Developing Teams

When a team is formed, it goes through progressive phases before its maturity level is reached. At these phases, the team can continuously make contributions to pay back all the efforts invested in the corporate up until the level of maturity.

Stages of Team Development

When the team matures, the participants grow slowly to face the challenges they encounter in their emotion and community. The team then undergoes very routine actions. The phases of team progression may variable in time and sequence because many things affect the development of the teams; the diversity of team members, their knowledge, their collaboration and the clarity of their roles.

Essentially, there are five phases of team creation in which most teams are involved: “forming, storming, norming, performing and adjourning.” The leaders will continue to understand and express more productive ways to work together by anticipating when and how they will treat team development by identifying those steps and assessing the existing level of functioning. Team leaders then need to establish a follow-up to ensure ongoing changes to results.

Figure 1: Phases of Team Development: Themes and Behaviours

3. METHODOLOGY

The research defined the features of successful teams at this level. Teams share a large number of similar attributes. The features of a literature quest and its results have been distilled to this effect. After that these features are understood, team members should be interviewed to assess if the features are successfully correlated with successful teams.

This qualitative research explored the attributes of successful corporate teams today, the effects of their corporate architecture on team growth and different ways, in which people know, interact and appreciate teams in the corporate world. The research included how teams were created, formed and controlled in these corporate.

Lists of six corporate following team-making processes were chosen. Interviewees and business identities are not disclosed for reasons of privacy. A summary of their corporate form, the location, income orientation and several employees are, however, revealed. Of use in data processing, a different case number was assigned.

4. ANALYSIS

In the case (1) initially, teams had been used but not productive and hence, dissolved in 1996. Many of the team leaders were mission-driven and the top management did not participate. The squad was not unified and there was overwhelming tension between team members.

In 2000, the Managing Director urged the management of the corporate to build additional teams. He told the team when they decided it was appropriate to discuss and determine for themselves their assignments. This versatility and ability to collaborate on issues of their choosing have certainly helped to create a team of trusted and inspired leaders. A group of 7 volunteers was created and started one hour a week. Yet the team nevertheless struggled to generate positive results after three months. They then agreed to employ a management consultant to help them overcome disputes and learn how to function more efficiently. The executive committee group had two sessions, but it made a difference. The respondent claimed that it is important to empower them to continue to function constructively. By then, the members of the team started to look at the same viewpoints and to understand and respect the perspective of another individual.

According to the review of literature, creating a high-productivity team may take a longer amount of time than may be required by the corporate. The timing of the storming phase depends on the competences of each team. The squad would also not give up in case (1) at the start. Members continued to communicate in various ways before the team become successful. According to Katz (1998) the managing director's proposal was appropriately designed to enable the team to work on their priorities. The team is driven to work more dependently on its actions, projects and decisions by choosing subjects for its choices. Members take responsibility for the performance of the project more directly. The outside input provided by the management consultant was a trigger for this team to lead to coherence within the team.

In the case (2) several teams were formed to carry out orders for the day. The teams depend on the number of requests and the ability of the employee to collaborate for a different team. Every team member sets a target that can be reached through development. If the goal is reached, they will earn a reward like a long paid leave. Teams are scored and compared with the expectations depending on the results of the day. If the corporate accumulate a certain level of reward, all full-time employees are equally divided. Each team heads by a leader, and if each team member is willing and accepted by the corporate, that they are equally eligible to become a leader. The sense of unity, teamwork and dedication is universal to all members of the team. As individuals, they create a unified team with a common goal in mind. A participant expressed that they are a "we" team instead of "I" team that is strongly differentiated by their performance or defeats and not as collective accomplishments.

The corporate structure is very flat and workforces believe like their views are taken to mean they are part of the corporate development. The accounting statements of the corporate are expressed collectively by all workforces. The corporate is committed to collaborating with its members to address challenges associated with the work of the team. A participant claimed that he was happy with his work, as the corporate cares, and he has a chance to improve and develop. Through the business choices, the corporate includes individuals from the supply chain with the hope that they can be involved and grasp corporate problems better. The hope is that everyone is more involved in resolving corporate challenges.

To become self-managed is an ambition that is not necessarily fulfilled when developing teams. Unrecognized habits are extinguished according to Huszczo (1996). The award services funded by the corporate also are important for the success of the squad. The belief that everyone in a team will become a team leader gives the workforce a clear feeling that the corporate is similarly autonomous and that team leader is motivated to take on responsibilities. For the team to create connection and dedication, the mechanics of a 'We' team are a surplus. Each member works as a team and is proud to be part of a team. Flatter corporate structure brings decision-making to all levels and can make the corporate more committed.

In the case (3) respondent had preceding experience working for a non-profit group with a significant number of volunteers. While the corporate has achieved volunteer retaining a feeble, teams have been formed to further dedicate themselves to perform the proposed tasks. Because of this corporate high turnover, a time during creating teams was a big concern. To order to speed up the entry of new numbers onto the team, the interviewee expressed to personally train potential participants before joining the squad.

Every individual's abilities were centred in particular, as each member has its ability to grow. The team members also believed that they were core elements of the project and the effort they spent appreciated. As a team leader, it is apparent from the interview that her role was to show others value. The exercise encouraged people to talk about their talents and the competences they could use to help. The interviewee concluded that the outcome of this corporate cooperation was greater efficiency, greater social values and greater workplace happiness.

While the new team members' preparation process can be handled accordingly, they find a very practical approach to speed up and facilitate a new team members' transition to the squad. An example of how much they are taken care of and valued is the individual recognition of the strengths of each person. This undoubtedly adds to the morale of each individual and creates efficiency and consumer attention.

In the case (4) cooperation is successfully done if workforces are shown to be equal. There is nobody in the project who has more influence than anyone else according to this interview. Employees feel themselves part of the squad and deserve recognition and integrity. The member is fully integrated with the squad after 90 days of orientation and there is no task that he or she cannot do. They are a huge group of individuals who are 100 % committed to team spirit. While the corporate has a formal structure, it shares its voice and balances rights. Team members create a combination of awareness, imagination and pleasure in their work environment.

Before such a policy was introduced, the workforce terrified when their supervisor visited them. But they are happy now that the supervisor visits them in their plant. Before, the workforce didn't have a lot of excitement at work, but now they have like the continuation of the family in their place of employment. Recently, they have built valuable outreach projects to increase awareness of their brand name and encourage more people to visit this outlet.

The team members are encouraged to think; their voices are heard and valued. It might also inspire them to take on more tasks and to be more dedicated to their work.

In the case (5) team bonding was very important; the manager's ideology was very significant in the process. If the teams are established, however, the manager ensures his maximum outreach with minimal intervention. To quickly integrate with the current team and introduce the team-building spirit in the firm, the corporate conduct a team-building exercise with new members. The staff has autonomy and can make mistakes in their operations. There is no financial compensation for such successes in this process. The team celebrates a pizza dinner; on the other hand, to honour squad successes and nominate every month successful employee to reveals his picture along with the appreciation of colleagues and other employees. Employees are rewarded for their accomplishments and an enjoyable work environment, the main elements noticed in the process.

For conventional corporate systems, decision-making and control to create partnerships within an enterprise can be very challenging for a community of individuals. Therefore, it will be important to assist and steer someone who inspired team growth. So after a team is formed and starts doing something, members should not think about themselves, so encourage them to think at work. They should also learn to plan. At the same time, the pattern of leaders working in teams can be seen in, Joinson (1999), as a prime example for team members.

The flexibility for the workforce to make mistakes means that the corporate encourages creativity successfully. Experiments are expected. Shaw (1995) states, however, that just twenty-four per cent of the teams surveyed received financial incentives for team accomplishments. What Shaw found became the most famous incentive - public appreciation. To order to optimize the prospective incentive, Antrim (1998) notes that certain corporate limit or even exclude "merit" increases to pay.

The Case (6) pronounces the idea that every team must provide a leader to articulate direction. The workforces are not doing a regular job is that they have a career. Technological advances and the implementation of new approaches to support clients are still in the process of evolving. This drive to follow different methods stems from versatility, control and the ability to improve the way they function. In the opinion of the interviewed person, some teams are failing because the members of these teams have not been honest enough to build artificial situations that produce artificial results.

The leader of a team is responsible for fostering communication, inspiration and commitment at all stages. Successful leaders are models who train, encourage and enable participants to take on more duties. The leadership position, therefore, involves allowing teams to become autonomous without the need for a supervisor to provide them with direction or to justify where they will go.

The research has found that the most important satisfiers are: fun at work and non-routine tasks where workers find like they are challenged and able to develop their skills. To improve workplace values, leaders have been found capable of granting greater responsibilities for their roles, encouraging staff to share business bonuses and ensuring that workforces meet their rights.

Interviews have identified the following characteristics in team members. The Team members will have: outstanding listening skills, the capacity to quickly relate to others show effort, problem-solving experience, competence in many areas, the sharpness of approaches for conflict management, leadership support, a sense of humour, resilience, endurance, versatility, accountability, innovation, openness to learning, level of engagement, particular attention to problems.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This research shows the factors affecting team performance and loss. Such aspects show that successful teams share similar attributes that help improve their projects and can contribute to higher rates of productivity by enhancing the efficiency of the entire corporate, including the production of its goods and the quality of its services. Consequently, when dealing with this corporate, this process can drive our customers to greater satisfaction, thus enabling customers to increase demand. The corporate benefits are focused on maintaining more customers for longer times and on increasing income for the corporate.

If a team works effectively together, participants may focus on their primary goals of solvent problems or process changes. However, the team results are poorly graded where there are unresolved disagreements among team members.

Teams have infinite capacity and can boost the corporate overall performance. Research has shown that teamwork provides a significant strategic advantage that can maximize corporate performance and increase profitability, competitiveness and employee satisfaction. To order to speed up and promote the completion of corporate goals, the team-building approach is being introduced. The corporate should always encourage their workforce to share the concept of team building to succeed in the long term.

Continuing efforts to keep workforce inspired and promote new ideas. Each member of the team must dedicate himself, one another and the corporate in general to feel the impact. The synergy between individuals to generate solutions and overcome challenges provides the foundation for corporate to develop teams. Teams can surpass what an individual alone can deliver. Teams are capable of generating synergy.

Conflict of Interest

The author confirms that there is no conflict of interest to declare for this publication.

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